

IS THIS BRUTALISM?

Or: How We Learned to Stop Worrying and Love the Rough

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Introduction.

“Is brutalism an architectural term for ugly? Speaking out of ignorance here, I’m an engineer.” This seemingly naïve remark caught our attention when it was made in response to an article about one of our early projects: the transformation of a stone ruin into a house in Ancede. At the conference Practices in Research #05 - Demolitions and Deconstructions, we found an opportunity to clarify our position on an enduring disciplinary debate — the ‘ethical or aesthetic?’ (R. Banham) nature of New Brutalism. As we see it, New Brutalism was clearly concerned with an attitude towards the process of thinking and making rather than with any specific material outcome. This also allowed us to explain why we believe its lessons on the ‘as found’ and ‘minimal intervention’ remain just as relevant today.

Contrary to what its association with *béton brut* might suggest, Brutalism is not synonymous with concrete. Instead, it embodies an attitude towards ordinariness and a particular sensitivity to the tangible material conditions of each project, whether constructed from wood, concrete masonry, or reclaimed stone. At the invitation of the editors, we now present a visual essay featuring images of two of our projects — firstly, the Studio-House in Valongo, and secondly, the House in Ancede — accompanied by captions that evoke and elaborate on some of the ideas behind them. Except for those specified, all images were made by Francisco Ascensão.

IS THIS BRUTALISM

Alison & Peter Smithson theorized about "The 'as-found', where the art is in the picking up, turning over and putting-with... And the "found", where the art is in the process and the watchful eye."
Photos: Studio-House, *atelier local*, 2018-2022.

Creating a new mezzanine in dialogue with an existing improvised structure places 'the new' and 'the old' on equal footing. The stone textures were preserved 'as found' to enhance the space's character, while plasterboard introduces smoother, more refined surfaces.

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The use of standard, everyday materials – some of which are not originally intended to remain exposed – enables a reduction in costs without sacrificing the creation of generous spaces with a strong expressive character. ©Francisco Ascensão + Luca Bosco

Brutalism embodies directness in relation to the existing. Existing wooden frames were neither replaced with new ones mimicking their design nor substituted with others deemed 'modern'. Just adding new frames on the interior allow the nearly 200-year-old sash frames to remain in place.

CHAPTER 2 DETAILS OF DEMOLITIONS

Perfection is not our aim, whether in the finishes or the overall appearance of materials. The marks left by the hands of those who built it are embraced as expressions of individuality that can neither be anticipated nor previously designed.

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For our project in Ancede, the original plan was to reconstruct an existing stone hut using a wooden structure and exposed cork insulation. However, a series of unforeseen events – including devastating wildfires, a global pandemic, and multiple wars leading to historic inflation rates – rendered this approach economically unfeasible. Our final proposal was to build the house anew, reusing every stone from the old ruin to create essential infrastructures such as retaining walls, a water tank, and exterior staircases. House in Ancede, *atelier local*, 2018-2023.

CHAPTER 2 DETAILS OF DEMOLITIONS

The decision to rebuild the house using concrete – including pillars, beams, floors, masonry walls, and ceilings – was not driven by ideological or aesthetic principles. Instead, it was as pragmatic as the original idea of rebuilding it in stone. The aim was to preserve the spatial intentions of our initial design while ensuring feasibility by leveraging the technical expertise of a local contractor. ©Luca Bosco (images below)

IS THIS BRUTALISM

Brutalism is about directness, which also entails embracing simpler ways of existing within the landscape by imbuing architecture with the energy inherent to its surroundings. Therefore, we see no particular reason why the bathroom cannot become the best place to read a book.

The ETICS insulation system was applied in a way that emphasises a certain imperfection, as well as a direct connection to the colour of the terrain. This colour does not come from an additional layer of paint but from the pigment within the mortar itself. The horizontal string courses lack a trim profile. The colour blends with the landscape, and the marks from its execution suggest its texture. The form of the house is a ready-made, replicating the volume of the old stone ruin.

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Alison & Peter Smithson believed that for brutalist architecture “the contractor should aim at a high standard of basic construction as in a small warehouse.” Filled horizontal joints contrast with dry vertical ones, to establish a distinct rhythm within the space. The composition of the exposed electrical circuits from catalogue pieces addresses the need for autonomous circuits, while giving purpose to their visibility. A vibrant colour elevates the status of inexpensive windows. Their positioning, aligned with the interior face of the wall, enhances the perception of a frame that captures the landscape. Their form invites different ways of appreciating it. It’s all about organising the construction language itself. We refer to these gestures as ‘functional ornaments’.

Practices in Research #05 - Demolitions and Deconstructions - December 2024

Online Open Access Double-Blind Peer-Reviewed Journal for Practice-Based Research in Architecture

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Thanks to Orfée Grandhomme & Ismaël Bennani

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ISSN: 2736-3996

Practices in Research Journal
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